

Human Resource Needs Planning in the Technical Implementation Unit Health Laboratory Kendari City

Ida Kusumajaya¹, Jafriati², Mubarak³

^{1,2,3} Postgraduate Study Program In Public Health, Haluoleo University, Kendari, Indonesia

ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Human Resource Planning Is A Structured Process Used To Predict Future Workforce Needs And Availability. Analysis Of Workforce Needs Is A Logical And Planned Step In Evaluating The Number And Competency Of Employees Required In An Organizational Unit. To Overcome The Problem Of Health Human Resource Needs, Laboratory Management Capabilities Are Needed To Accurately Plan Health Human Resource Needs In Accordance With Existing Service Requirements In Each Laboratory Unit. .

Method: This Research Aims To Carry Out An Analysis Of Health Human Resource Needs Planning At The Kendari City Health Laboratory Service Technical Implementation Unit. This Type Of Research Is Qualitative Descriptive Research With A Case Study Approach. The Informants In This Study Were 6 People, 2 Informants At The Service Technical Implementation Unit Health Laboratory And 4 Informants At The Kendari City Health Service. Data Collection Was Obtained From Primary Data And Secondary Data Through In-Depth Interviews, Document Review And Literature Review. Data Analysis Techniques Include Data Reduction, Data Presentation And Drawing Conclusions.

Results And Conclusions: The Research Results Show That In Planning Health Human Resources Needs There Is No Standard Operating Procedure, There Is No Policy In The Form Of A Planning Team Decree, There Is No Budget In Human Resources Planning, The Availability Of Data And Information Systems In The Form Of The Human Resources Application And The Renbut Application, And Using The Workload Analysis Method In Calculating Human Resources Needs.

KEYWORDS: Human Resources, Laboratory, Planning.

INTRODUCTION

In Order To Achieve Health Development Targets, Comprehensive Efforts Are Needed To Meet Health Needs With The Support Of Health Resources, Including The Provision Of Adequate And Evenly Distributed Health Human Resources In All Health Service Facilities Throughout Indonesia ⁽¹⁾.

The Availability Of Quality Human Resources (Hr) For Health, Sufficient, Evenly Distributed, Effective And Efficient In Their Utilization Is Very Important In A Sustainable Manner To Ensure The Implementation Of Health Development With The Aim Of Improving The Highest Level Of Public Health. ⁽¹⁾.

Article 12 Of Law Number 17 Of 2023 Concerning Health Stipulates That The Central Government And Regional Governments Are Responsible For Planning, Procuring And Utilizing Medical Personnel And Health Workers In Accordance With The Needs Of The Community And Their Region Based On The Provisions Of Statutory Regulations ⁽²⁾.

Human Resource Planning Is A Structured Process Used To Predict Future Workforce Needs And Availability. More Simply, Workforce Needs Analysis Is A Logical And Planned Step In Evaluating The Number And Competency Of Employees Needed In An Organizational Unit. This Aims To Ensure That Each Team Member In The Organizational Unit Has A Role That Is Appropriate To Their Duties And Responsibilities⁽³⁾. Based On Several Studies, It Shows That Health Human Resources Have A Major Role In Achieving The Success Of Health Development Goals.

The Success Of A Health Service In An Organization Can Be Seen From The Availability Of Health Human Resources. Human Resource Planning Is The Main Function That Must Be Carried Out By Every Organization And Must Be The Focus Of Attention So That The Steps Taken By Management Are Appropriate, Ensuring That Within The Organization The Right Health Workers

Are Available To Occupy The Right Positions And Jobs On Time. Appropriate In Order To Achieve A Goal And Various Targets That Have Been Set ⁽⁴⁾.

One Of The Main Challenges In The Health System Is The Shortage Of Health Human Resources (Hr). To Ensure Equitable Distribution And Effective Deployment Of Health Workers, Current And Timely Information About Health Workers Is Essential. Health Workforce Data Collection Has The Potential To Collect Data That Can Be Used In Evidence-Based Human Resource Planning And Policy Making ⁽⁵⁾.

Planning Health Human Resource (Hr) Needs Is A Top Priority To Ensure The Availability, Distribution And Improvement Of The Quality Of Health Human Resources. Planning For Health Human Resource Needs At The District/City Level Begins With Evaluating Policies Related To Health Human Resource Planning, Ensuring The Competency Of Planners, And Paying Attention To The Availability Of Supporting Financing. In The Planning Process, Efforts Will Be Made To Utilize Appropriate Data And Information Systems, As Well As Apply Methods And Calculations Of Needs In Accordance With Established Standards. This Is Expected To Produce Output In The Form Of Planning Health Human Resource Needs ⁽⁶⁾.

In Al-Sawai And Al-Shishtawy's Research, They Stated That Poor Health Human Resource Planning Has Resulted In An Imbalance That Can Threaten The Capacity Of The Health Service System To Achieve Its Goals. This Encourages A Focus On The Potential For Developing Health Care Systems That Are More Responsive To The Needs And Expectations Of Society, By Providing A Systematic Approach For Health Planners To Effectively Manage Human Resources In The Health Sector ⁽⁷⁾.

One Important Effort To Overcome The Problem Of Health Human Resource Needs Is The Ability Of Laboratory Management To Accurately Plan Health Human Resource Needs In Accordance With Existing Service Requirements In Each Laboratory Unit. One Sign Of The Success Of A Laboratory That Operates Effectively And Efficiently Is The Availability Of Human Resources Appropriate To The Number, Type, Competency And Qualifications Required To Fulfill Individual Functions And Tasks.

The Initial Survey Conducted At The Kendari City Health Laboratory Service Technical Implementation Unit Found That The Number Of Human Resources Was 10 People Consisting Of The Head Of The Laboratory, Head Of Tu Subdivision, 2 Health Analyst Staff, 1 Chemical Analyst, 1 Nurse, 1 Epidemiology Staff, 2 Health Administration Staff And 1 Midwife. Apart From The Placement Of Employees Who Are Not In Accordance With Their Expertise, Namely Epidemiologists As Those Responsible For Media And Reagents And Concurrently Serving As Treasurers, Midwives As Those Responsible For Sterilizing Equipment And Those Responsible For Cleaning.

It Is Known That The Health Human Resources (Hr) Planning At The Kendari City Health Laboratory Service Technical Implementation Unit Was Prepared Only To Summarize The Proposed Health Worker Needs Submitted To The Kendari City Health Service. There Is No Complete Health Human Resources (Hr) Planning Document Yet Because There Is A Shortage Of Staff And There Is No Hr Planning Team. Apart From That, Obstacles Include The Unavailability Of Allocated Funds For Planning, The Human Resource Information System Has Not Been Used Optimally And There Are No Standard Work Procedures In Implementing Hr Planning. The Planning Process Is Also Not Carried Out Through Systematic, Continuous Stages And Careful Consideration So That Often The Health Workers Placed By The Kendari City Health Service Do Not Match The Real Needs Proposed By The Kendari City Health Laboratory Service Technical Implementation Unit.

Based On Existing Data And Problems, The Author Is Interested In Conducting Research To Obtain In-Depth Information About Planning Health Human Resource Needs At The Kendari City Health Laboratory Service Technical Implementation Unit. The Aim Of This Research Is To Carry Out An Analysis Of Hr Needs Planning At The Kendari City Health Laboratory Service Technical Implementation Unit.

RESEARCH METHODS

This Research Was Conducted Using A Qualitative Descriptive Research Method With A Case Study Approach, Which Aims To Dig Deeper Into Information About Health Human Resource (Hr) Planning At The Kendari City Health Laboratory Service Technical Implementation Unit By Involving Collection From Various Sources Of Information. There Were 6 Informants In This Study. People, 2 Informants From The Service Technical Implementation Unit Kendari City Health Laboratory And 4 Informants From The Kendari City Health Service. The Research Was Conducted In December 2023 At The Kendari City Health Laboratory Service Technical Implementation Unit And The Kendari City Health Service. Data Collection Techniques Involve In-Depth Interviews, Observation And Document Review, While Data Analysis Is Carried Out In 3 Steps, Namely Data Reduction, Data Presentation And Drawing Conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Standard Operating Procedures

Standard Operating Procedures Are A Series Of Standardized Written Instructions Regarding The Various Processes Of Carrying Out Organizational Activities, How And When They Must Be Carried Out, Where And By Whom They Are Carried Out ⁽⁸⁾.

The Results Of Research On Standard Operating Procedures (Sop) Show That The Kendari City Health Laboratory Service Technical Implementation Unit Does Not Yet Have An Official Sop That Has Been Established As A Guideline For Planning Human Resource Needs.

Planning For Human Resource Needs In The Health Laboratory Is Web-Based, All Calculation Activities Are Directly Entered Into The Renbut Application And The Calculation Results Can Be Directly Seen By The Renbut Admin At The Kendari City Health Service, Making It Easier For Planning Staff. Because Hr Planning Is Now Considered Easier Because It Is No Longer Done Manually, Planning Sop Are Deemed No Longer Necessary To Be Created.

To Facilitate The Steps In Planning Hr Needs, An Official Sop Needs To Be Created So That Each Planning Staff Can Use The Sop As A Guide In Hr Planning So That If There Is A Transfer Of Planning Staff Within An Organization, The New Planning Staff Can Follow The Hr Planning Steps As Stated In The Sop Which Has Been Standardized.

Standard Operational Procedures For Human Resources Planning Are Very Important For An Organization Because They Help In Managing The Planning Process, Developing Human Resources Efficiently And Effectively. According To Researchers, Several Benefits Are Why Sop Are Very Important To Create In Human Resources Planning, Namely: (1) Sop Are Clear Guidelines And Systems For Implementing Human Resources Planning Steps Consistently And Effectively, (2) Sop Help Ensure That The Human Resources Planning Process Resources Are Carried Out In Accordance With Applicable Standards And Regulations, Thereby Reducing The Risk Of Errors And Violations. (3) With The Sop, Human Resources Planning Can Be Carried Out In A Structured And Measurable Manner. This Makes It Easier To Monitor And Evaluate The Achievement Of Planning Goals. (4) Sop Help In Conveying Human Resources Planning Steps To All Parties Involved, So That Everyone Understands The Steps That Must Be Taken (5) Clear Sop Enable Management And Related Staff To Make More Appropriate Workforce Planning Decisions.

It Is Important To Prepare Official Sop To Increase Awareness Of Responsibilities Related To The Use Of The Renbut Application. This Aims To Make The Performance Of Officers In Reporting Human Resources Needs Planning More Timely, Organized And Optimal Because They Have Guidelines That Make It Easier To Carry Out Their Duties. ⁽⁹⁾.

Policy

Policy Is A Series Of Concepts And Principles That Form The Basis Of Plans In Carrying Out Tasks, Leadership And Actions (Especially In The Context Of Government, Organizations, Etc.), It Is Also A Statement Regarding Ideals, Goals, Principles And Guidelines For Management In An Effort To Achieve Set Goals. ⁽¹⁰⁾. The Main Resource In Policy Implementation Is Staff ⁽¹¹⁾. In Planning Human Resources Needs, Staff Are Needed As Planning Staff. Human Resource Planners Should Ideally Be Able To Inventory Data From Various Agencies, Then Analyze It According To The Planning Method Options To Produce A Human Resources Needs Planning Document That Can Be Accounted For. This Analysis Includes The Gap Between Availability And Need, Projected Needs Within A Certain Time Period, As Well As A Region-Based Human Resources Distribution Map ⁽⁶⁾.

This Research Shows That The Kendari City Health Laboratory Service Technical Implementation Unit Does Not Have A Planning Team To Carry Out Planning For Health Human Resources Needs. The Calculation Of Health Human Resources Needs Is Carried Out By Planning Staff, Namely The Head Of The Kendari City Health Laboratory Administration Subsection. Meanwhile, At The Kendari City Health Service, There Is A Policy In The Form Of A Decision Letter From The Health Human Resources Planning Team Which Was Determined By The Mayor Of Kendari. The Planning Team Consists Of The Head Of The Health Service, Head Of The Sdk Division Of The Health Service, Human Resources Coordinator Of The Health Service, Manager Of The Health Service's Needs Plan, General, Personnel And Legal Subdivision Of The Health Service, Head Subdivision Of Governance Management Of The Kendari City Regional Secretariat Organization Bureau And Head Of Development And Transfers Of The Kendari City Regional Personnel Agency. Planning Personnel In All Service Technical Implementation Units Of The Health Service Are Not Included In The Planning Team Decree Even Though They Carry Out Planning For Human Resources Needs From The Lower Level. Based On The Results Of Interviews With Informants, Planners At The Service Technical Implementation Unit Level Were Not Included In The Decree Of The Kendari City Health Service Human Resources Planning Team Because The Service Technical Implementation Unit Planners Were Only Users.

The Kendari City Level Health Human Resources Planning Team Was Prepared By The Kendari City Health Service Referring To The Republic Of Indonesia Minister Of Health Regulation Number 33 Of 2015 Where The Human Resources Needs Planning Team Consists Of A Steering Team Which Is Stakeholders At The Policy Making Level And An Implementation Team Which Consists Of Stakeholders. Interests At The Implementing Level Of Drafting Human Resources Requirements Planning Documents. Implementation Team That Facilitates And Assists Institutions In Calculating Health Human Resources Needs.

A Human Resources Needs Planning Team Was Not Formed At The Kendari City Health Laboratory Because Even Though There Is Only One Planning Staff, Human Resources Needs Planning Can Still Be Carried Out. A Planning Team Can Be Formed If The Planning Staff Are No Longer Able To Plan Human Resources Needs Themselves.

Service Technical Implementation Kendari City Health Laboratory Unit As An Organization Needs To Create A Human Resources Planning Team Which Can Be Determined Through A Decree From The Head Of The Laboratory, So That Planning For Human Resources Needs Can Be Carried Out By Several People In The Planning Team So That If There Is A Transfer Of One Of The Planning Staff There Is Still There Are Other Planners Who Have Competence In Planning Human Resources Needs In The Laboratory.

Based On Research Results Sumiarsih And Nurlinawati (2020), Stated That Problems In Health Human Resources Planning Were Still Found In The Aspect Of Low Competency Of Planning Staff. The Regional Government's Commitment Is Considered Not Yet Optimal In Terms Of Facilitating Capacity Building For Health Human Resources Planners. This, From A Broader Perspective, Will Hamper The Running Of The Organization Because The Type And Number Of Health Human Resources Needed Cannot Be Calculated Accurately⁽⁶⁾.

Budget

A Budget Is A Plan Expressed In The Form Of Numbers. Apart From Functioning As A Planning Tool, The Budget Also Acts As A Control Tool⁽¹²⁾.

The Results Of Research On Budget Support Influence The Quality Of Health Human Resources Planning In Laboratories. The Limited Ability Of Planners To Plan Human Resources Needs In The Laboratory Is Due To A Lack Of Competence. Existing Budget Limitations Cause Organizations To Be Unable To Carry Out Activities In An Effort To Increase The Competency Of Human Resources Planners.

In 2023, The Health Human Resources Planning Staff At The Kendari City Health Laboratory Service Technical Implementation Unit Will Not Plan Health Human Resources Needs, This Is Known From The Planning Document Prepared By The Kendari City Health Service, Where In The Needs Planning Document There Are No Proposed Needs Health Human Resources From The Kendari City Health Laboratory Service Technical Implementation Unit.

There Is No Special Budget Available For Planning Human Resources Needs Because It Was Never Proposed By The Kendari City Health Laboratory Unit Technical Implementation Service. Planning Activities Through The Renbut Application Make It Easier For Laboratories To Calculate Human Resources Needs So That There Is No Need For A Special Budget, While Activities To Increase Competency For Laboratory Planning Staff And Preparing Human Resources Needs Planning Documents Are The Main Duties Of The Health Service Human Resources Coordinator So That The Budget For Planning Health Human Resources Needs Can Be Achieved. Carried Out At The Health Service. The Human Resources Section, As A Coordinator In Planning Human Resources Needs At The Health Service, Has Proposed A Budget, But The Existing Budget Is Insufficient To Carry Out Competency Improvement Training For Planning Staff At Lower Levels, Such As Planning Staff In Laboratories.

Research Conducted By Sumiarsih And Nurlinawati (2020), Stated That One Of The Obstacles In Planning Human Resources For Health Is The Lack Of Seriousness Of Local Governments In Providing Budgets To Increase The Capacity Of Planners And To Carry Out Follow-Up Actions On Human Resources Needs Planning Documents. Health. Ideally, Health Human Resources Planners Have The Ability To Collect Data From Various Agencies, Carry Out Analyzes According To Various Planning Methods, And Produce Accountable Health Human Resources Needs Planning Documents. This Analysis Includes An Assessment Of The Gap Between Availability And Needs, Projections Of Needs Within A Certain Time Period, As Well As A Map Of The Distribution Of Health Human Resources By Region⁽⁶⁾.

Availability Of Data And Information Systems

Quality, Up-To-Date And Reliable Data About Human Resources In The Health Sector Is A Key Factor In Strengthening The Health System. In Order To Be Used Effectively, Both At The National And Regional Levels, Information Regarding Human Resources

In The Health Sector Must Be Integrated Into An Easily Accessible Information System. ⁽¹³⁾. The Health Information System Is A System That Provides Information That Supports The Decision-Making Process At Various Levels Of Health Administration, Both At The Health Effort Implementation Unit Level, At The District/City Level, At The Provincial Level, And At The Central Level ⁽¹⁴⁾.

The Information System At The Service Technical Implementation Unit Kendari City Health Laboratory Uses A Web-Based Information System That Allows Fast And Easy Access. The Web-Based Information System Is The Human Resources Application And The Renbut Application. The Health Human Resources Information System Application Contains Health Human Resources Data And Information, While The Renbut Application Is An Application Used To Calculate Health Human Resources Needs. To Be Able To Access These Two Applications, Health Facilities Such As Laboratories Must Have An Account Registered With The Human Resources Health Information System Application Socialization First And The Renbut Application, Which Can Then Be Accessed Via A Browser, Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox.

According To Hasnadi (2023), In His Research Stated That With The Availability Of Fast And Accurate Information, Management Can More Easily Plan Human Resources Based On Advanced Technology. This Is A Necessity That Cannot Be Avoided In An Era Of Rapid Change⁽¹⁵⁾.

Methods And Calculations Of Health Human Resources Needs

In The Regulation Of The Minister Of Health Of The Republic Of Indonesia Number 33 Of 2015, There Are Two Methods For Planning Human Resources Health Needs At The Institutional Level Which Are Adapted To The Intended Use, Namely (1) The Abk Health Method For Calculating Human Resources Needs In Health Facilities In District/City Regional Government Areas, Based On Workload And (2) Minimum Manpower Standard Methods, To Determine The Need For Health Service Facilities (Hospitals And Health Centers) With Permits To Establish New Or Increase The Classification Of Health Service Facilities In District/City Regional Government Areas, As Well As In Remote Area Health Service Facilities, Are Very Remote, Border, Underdeveloped, And Areas That Are Not Of Interest.

This Research Shows That Planning For Health Human Resources Needs At The Kendari City Health Service And Technical Implementation Units Under The Health Service Such As The Service Technical Implementation Unit Health Laboratory Has Been Implemented Based On A Web Application. In This Application There Are 2 Methods For Calculating Human Resources, Namely The Workload Analysis (Abk) Method Which Is Used To Calculate Human Resources In Hospitals And Inpatient Health Centers, While The Minimum Manpower Standard Method Is Intended For Calculating Human Resources For Outpatient Health Centers. The Method Used By The Kendari City Health Laboratory In Planning Human Resources Needs Is The Workload Analysis (Abk) Method.

Based On Research Permatasari Dan Pudjirahardjo (2015), Stated That The Application Of The Wisn/Abk Method Must Be Supported By In-Depth Analysis And Not Easily Accept The Final Results Obtained. Thus, The Application Of The Abk Method Can Produce Accurate Results If The Calculated Classification Of Personnel Has Carried Out Their Duties In Accordance With The Main Duties Of Work Determined Through Job Analysis.⁽¹⁶⁾

Planning For Health Human Resources Needs

The Human Resource Planning System Includes Estimation, Demand And Supply Of Labor In An Organization. If Human Resource Needs Are Not Planned Well, It Can Result In A Shortage Of Workers Which Can Affect Patient Service And Comfort, As Well As Increase The Workload For Health Workers. ⁽¹⁷⁾.

The Results Of This Research Show That The Planning For Health Human Resources Needs In The Kendari City Health Laboratory's Technical Service Implementation Unit Was Carried Out For The First Time In 2021 On A Web Basis Because They Had Just Received Users Of The Renbut Application From The Health Service. For Health Human Resources Planning Before 2021, The Health Laboratory Is Still Within One Unit Of The Kendari City Health Service So It Never Receives A Human Resources Allocation. To Meet The Shortage Of Human Resources The Kendari City Health Laboratory Invites Requests To The Kendari City Health Service. The Request For Personnel Is Only In The Form Of A Letter Requesting Personnel Requirements, Not Yet Accompanied By A Detailed Planning Document Regarding The Analysis Of The Human Resources Needed So That The Personnel Distributed By The Health Service Often Do Not Match The Competencies Required By The Laboratory.

Sumiarsih Dan Nurlinawati (2020), Stated That Problems In Health Human Resources Planning Are Still Often Found At The Input And Process Stages, Which Have An Impact On The Output Or Output Human Resources Gaps At Various Levels Of Government

In Indonesia. The Main Problems Include Complex Regional Government Policies And Management Of The State Civil Service (Asn), Low Competence Of Planning Staff, And Minimal Financial Support. Problems In The Process Include The Use Of Data And Information Systems That Are Not Yet Optimal, As Well As A Lack Of Understanding And Implementation Of Proper Preparation Of Human Resources Needs. Meanwhile, The Problem In Output Is The Human Resources Gap Related To The Number And Type Of Adequate Health Workers⁽⁶⁾.

CONCLUSION

Based On The Results Of This Research, It Can Be Concluded That In Planning Health Human Resources Needs At The Service Technical Implementation Unit Kendari City Health Laboratory There Is No Sop For Planning Health Human Resources Needs, There Is No Policy In The Form Of A Decision Letter From The Health Human Resources Needs Planning Team, There Is No Budget Provided Specifically For Planning Activities For Health Human Resources Needs, For The Availability Of Human Resources Data And Information Systems In Planning Human Resources Needs In The Form Of The Human Resources Application And Renbut Application, And The Method Used In Planning Human Resources Needs Uses The Workload Analysis (Abk) Method.

REFERENCES

1. Kemenkes Ri. Peraturan Menteri Kesehatan Republik Indonesia Nomor 33 Tahun 2015 Tentang Pedoman Penyusunan Perencanaan Kebutuhan Sumber Daya Manusia Kesehatan [Internet]. Indonesia; 2015 P. 1–27. Available From: [https://Peraturan.Bpk.Go.Id/Download/106972/Permenkes Nomor 33 Tahun 2015.Pdf](https://Peraturan.Bpk.Go.Id/Download/106972/Permenkes%20Nomor%2033%20Tahun%202015.Pdf)
2. Undang-Undang Ri. Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 17 Tahun 2023 Tentang Kesehatan [Internet]. 17 Indonesia; 2023 P. 1–300. Available From: [https://Peraturan.Bpk.Go.Id/Download/314883/Uu Nomor 17 Tahun 2023.Pdf](https://Peraturan.Bpk.Go.Id/Download/314883/Uu%20Nomor%2017%20Tahun%202023.Pdf)
3. Paruntu Brl, Rattu Ajm, Tilaar Cr. Perencanaan Kebutuhan Sumber Daya Manusia Di Puskesmas Kabupaten Minahasa Human Resource Requirements Planning In Health Center Minahasa District. 2015;43–53.
4. Nuryati, Eko Pa, Anita W. Perencanaan Kebutuhan Tenaga Rekam Medis Dengan Metode Workload Indicators Of Staffing Need (Wisn) Di Puskesmas Gondokusuman Ii Kota Yogyakarta. 2016;1–23.
5. Chibuzor M, Arikpo I, Aquaisua E, Esu E, Okoroafor Sc, Omar S, Et Al. Implementation Of Health Workforce Information Systems: A Review Of Eight Sub-Saharan Country Experiences. *J Public Heal (United Kingdom)*. 2021;43:127–40.
6. Sumiarsih M, Nurlinawati I. Permasalahan Dalam Perencanaan Kebutuhan Sumber Daya Manusia Kesehatan Di Kabupaten/Kota. *J Penelit Dan Pengemb Pelayanan Kesehat*. 2020;3(3):182–92.
7. Al-Sawai A, Al-Shishtawy Mm. Health Workforce Planning. *Revis Recd*. 2015;15(16):27–33.
8. Kemenpan & Rb Ri. Pedoman Penyusunan Standar Operasional Prosedur. Permenpan Nomor 21 Tahun 2008 Tentang Pedoman Penyusunan Standar Operasional Prosedur Administrasi Pemerintahan Jakarta; 2012 P. 1–63.
9. Zainatunningtias L, Prasastin Ov. Evaluasi Penggunaan Aplikasi Renbut 4.0 Terhadap Perencanaan Kebutuhan Tenaga Kesehatan Dalam Meningkatkan Mutu Pelayanan Kesehatan Di Puskesmas Colomadu Ii Karanganyar. *Dr Diss Univ Kusuma Husada Surakarta [Internet]*. 2022;1–11. Available From: <http://Www.Renbut.Kemkes.Go.Id/>
10. Taufiqurokhman. Kebijakan Publik. In: *Kebijakan Publik*. 2014. P. 15.
11. Igirisa I. Kebijakan Publik. Muhammad I, Editor. Yogyakarta: Tanah Air Beta; 2022. 1–208 P.
12. Taufiqurokhman. Konsep Dan Kajian Ilmu Perencanaan [Internet]. Fakultas Ilmu Sosial Dan Ilmu Politik Universitas Prof. Dr. Moestopo Beragama. 2008. Available From: <http://Fisip.Moestopo.Ac.Id/Storage/Buku/Buku-04-Taufiqurokhman-Konsep-Dan-Kajian-Ilmu-Perencanaan-Belum-Isbn.Pdf>
13. Bpphuman Resourcesk Ri. Peta Jalan (Road Map) Sistem Informasi Human Resources Kesehatan Di Indonesia. In Jakarta; 2021. P. 1–89.
14. Susanto Eb, Kurniawan Mf, Christianto Pa. Integrasi Informasi Kesehatan Pada Instansi Kesehatan Di Kota Pekalongan Melalui Sistem Informasi Layanan Kesehatan. *J Litbang Kota Pekalongan*. 2017;13:31–9.
15. Hasnadi. Perencanaan Sumber Daya Manusia. *Perisai J Pendidik Dan Ris Ilmu Sains*. 2023;2(3):338–49.
16. Permatasari Ed, Pudjirahardjo Wj. Kelemahan Workload Indicators Of Staffing Need Sebagai Metode Perhitungan Jumlah Kebutuhan Tenaga Kesehatan Di Puskesmas. 2015;2015:1–239. Available From: <https://Media.Neliti.Com/Media/Publications/72519-Id-None.Pdf>

17. Hajriati Isma, Arman, Muchlis Nurmiati. Analisis Sistem Perencanaan Tenaga Kesehatan Di Wilayah Kerja Dinas Kesehatan Kabupaten Barru. J Muslim Community Heal [Internet]. 2021;2(4):103–16. Available From: <https://doi.org/10.52103/Jmch.V2i4.700>